

Evaluation of Fermentation Quality and Nutritional Properties of Teff and Guar Mixed Silage

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Abstract

Mixed silage production using protein-rich legumes and water-soluble carbohydrate-rich cereals is widely practiced to enhance silage fermentation and nutritional quality. This study aimed to investigate the effects of teff (T) and guar (G) silage, mixed in varying proportions, on fermentation and nutritional characteristics. For this purpose, teff and guar plants were combined in five different ratios (100%T, 75%T+25%G, 50%T+50%G, 25%T+75%G, and 100%G) based on their dry matter content. The prepared silages were opened after 60 days. pH measurements were taken, and samples were dried at 70 °C to determine dry matter content. Dried samples were analyzed for crude protein, crude fat, crude ash, ADF, NDF, and gas-methane production. Silage juice samples were extracted to determine organic acid content (lactic, acetic, butyric, and propionic acids) and elucidate fermentation characteristics. According to the study results, when ADF and NDF contents were examined, the best results were obtained from 100% teff silage as 29.85% and 43.66%, respectively. The 100% Guar treatment exhibited the highest crude fat ratio (2.74%), dry matter ratio (27.18%), and crude ash ratio (10.73%). The 75% guar + 25% teff mixture produced the highest crude protein ratio at 17.34%. The best result in pH value was determined as 4.23 in 25%G+75%T mixture silage. The highest lactic acid concentration (7.53%) was found in the 100% teff silage. Acetic acid ratio was determined with 1.67% in 100% teff silage, butyric acid ratio was determined with 0% and 25%G+75%T and 100% teff silage, propionic acid ratio was determined with 0.36% in 100% teff silage. While ETOH value decreased in mixed silages with increasing teff ratio, *in vitro* gas, ME value, OMD value and fleig score increased. At the end of the study, G50 + T50 and G25 + T75 mixture ratios are recommended in terms of both nutritional and fermentation properties of the mixture silage. The data obtained from this research presents high-quality alternative silage materials for animal nutrition.

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1. Introduction

Silo feeds are indispensable roughage sources in the nutrition of ruminant animals. The fact that feed costs are quite high in animal production increases the importance of silo feeds even more. Silo feed is widely used in developed countries and silage constitutes an important part of rations (Sarıçiçek et al., 2002). Recently, silage has become one of the most important components of dairy rations to meet ruminant requirements due to low nutrient loss from harvest to storage, easy feeding and handling, and higher yields (Mahanna and Chase, 2015). In most parts of the world, silage production of crops such as green cereals, maize, sorghum, alfalfa and soybeans has recently increased more than use as hay or grazing (Kizilsimsek et al., 2017). Silage, a fermented, high-moisture stored feed used to feed ruminant animals during periods when fresh feed is not available, is a critical component in livestock production systems. Silage making, the process of creating silage, preserves the nutritional value of forage crops, balances feed supply and improves the digestibility of fibrous materials. The success of silage production depends largely on the quality of the forage crops used, the management of the fermentation process and the interaction between different plant species when blended silages are combined (Du et al., 2023). Despite the widespread use of teff (*Eragrostis tef* L.), a cereal crop native to Ethiopia, as a staple food (Tanik and Kökten, 2021), its potential for silage production as a forage crop has not been extensively investigated. However, its nutrient profile suggests that it could be an excellent candidate for silage when combined with other crops that complement its characteristics (Gelaw and Qureshi, 2020). Guar bean is a plant that is resistant to heat and drought (Singh Santos, 2014), has high yield, rich in pods, leaves and protein and can be harvested 3-4 months after sowing (Suliman et al., 2017). In terms of these characteristics, it is suitable for cultivation in regions where teff agriculture is practiced. In addition to growing in unfavorable environmental conditions, it has high protein content and low cell wall components

(Kusvuran et al., 2019). Making silage by mixing plants with high soluble carbohydrates and plants with high protein is a good way to obtain a quality feed (Cürek and Özen, 2004). Guar bean is a plant that is resistant to heat and drought (Singh Santos, 2014), has high yield, rich in pods, leaves and protein and can be harvested 3-4 months after sowing (Suliman et al., 2017). In terms of these characteristics, it is suitable for cultivation in regions where teff agriculture is practiced. In addition to growing in unfavorable environmental conditions, it has high protein content and low cell wall components (Kusvuran et al., 2019). Making silage by mixing plants with high soluble carbohydrates and plants with high protein is a good way to obtain a quality feed (Cürek and Özen, 2004). Guar bean seems to be a good pair for mixing with teff to make a quality silage. Quality has been improved in blended silages with many different legumes such as sorghum, soybean (Lima et al., 2011; Ni et al., 2018), lablab bean (Contreras-Govea et al., 2011), jack bean and velvet bean (Lima-Orozco et al., 2014). This study aims to contribute to the development of a high quality, nutritionally balanced silage that can be used to increase livestock productivity using teff and guar plants.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Silage preparation

In the study, teff and guar were used as silage materials. Guar beans were harvested at pod set and teff at milk-pulp stage. The plants were chopped into 2-3 cm long pieces using a chopper. Samples were prepared as T100: 100% tef, T75G25: 75% teff + 25% guar, T50G50: 50% teff + 50% guar, T25G75: 25% teff + 75% guar and G100: 100% guar. The chopped samples were homogeneously mixed and filled into 2 kg vacuum bags, then the air was removed, sealed and stored in a dark place at 24±2 °C for 60 days. Silages were prepared in three replications.

2.2. Biochemical analysis

After 60 days, 30 g sample taken from the opened silage was mixed with 270 ml of pure water and pH was measured. Dry matter

content was determined by drying 500 g of silage samples in an oven at 70 °C until the weight remained constant. The dried samples were ground in a mill with a sieve diameter of 1 mm and prepared for chemical analysis. Crude ash rate of silage samples was determined by incineration of the samples at 550 °C for 8 hours. Crude oil analysis was performed using ether extraction and a Soxhlet collector (AOAC, 1990). Nitrogen (N) content of silages was determined using the Kjeldahl method and crude protein rate was calculated using the formula $N \times 6.25$ (AOAC, 1990). Fiber analysis (acid detergent and neutral detergent fiber) was performed using the methods recommended by ANKOM Tech (2017).

2.3. Organic acid analysis

For organic acid analysis, 5 g silage samples were taken and homogenized in 5% metaphosphoric acid for 2 minutes. These samples were then centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 5 min, the top layer was removed and transferred to HPLC tubes after membrane filtering and analyzed. Organic acid analysis of silage samples was performed using Shimadzu Prominence series (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC). Chromatographic separation was performed with 0.5% metaphosphoric acid in Eluent A and acetonitrile in Eluent B. The flow rate during all organic acid separations was 0.6 ml/min and Prodigy 5 μ ODS (2) HPLC column was used for organic acid analysis with DAD detector (Barker and Summerson, 1941).

2.4. *In vitro* gas and methane production

The rumen fluid required for *in vitro* gas measurements was obtained from three ivesi sheep with fistulas. Water and licking stones were provided to the sheep at all times. Rumen fluid was taken before the morning feeding, filtered through a fourfold cheesecloth and mixed with buffer solution at a ratio of 1:2. Approximately 0.2 grams of the ground samples were weighed into a 100 ml syringe. Then 30 ml of buffered rumen fluid was transferred into the syringe. The syringes containing the sample and rumen fluid were placed in a 39 °C water bath. In addition, four syringes containing only buffered rumen fluid without sample were included in the incubation. The gas measurements obtained from these syringes were subtracted from the gases obtained from all syringes to determine the net gas production. The feeds were incubated for 24 hours and the total gases released were determined. The obtained gases were transferred to an Infrared Methane Analyzer (Sensor Europe GmbH, Erkrath, Germany) with the help of a plastic syringe and methane production was determined (Goel et al., 2008). The methane content of the gas injected into the Infrared Methane Analyzer was measured in %. The following formula was used to calculate methane production. Methane production (ml) = Total gas (mL) X Methane (%).

2.5. Determination of metabolic energy (ME) value and organic matter digestibility (OMD) of feeds

The metabolic energy content of the feeds was calculated by using some parameters of twenty-four hours gas production and chemical composition by the following formula (Menke and Steingass, 1988).

$$\text{OMD, \%} = 15.38 + 0.8453 \times \text{GP} + 0.0595 \times \text{CP} + 0.0675 \times \text{CA}$$

$$\text{ME, MJ/kg DM} = 2.20 + 0.1357 \times \text{GP} + 0.0057 \times \text{CP} + 0.0012859 \times \text{CO}^2$$

In these equations;

OMD = Organic matter digestibility; ME = Metabolic energy; GP = Twenty-four hour gas production (ml); CP = Crude protein (g kg⁻¹ dry matter); CO = Crude oil (g kg⁻¹ dry matter); CA = Crude ash (g kg⁻¹ dry matter).

2.6. Statistical analysis

The findings obtained from the research were subjected to analysis of variance according to the randomized blocks experimental design using (SAS analysis software, 1999) package program. The significance of the difference between the averages was determined by LSD test.

3. Results and Discussion

Biochemical properties of teff and guar mixture silages are given in Table 1. The effect of mixture ratios on the biochemical properties of silages was found to be statistically very significant ($P \leq 0.01$). In G100 silage, ADF and NDF were the highest with 45.35% and 62.18%, respectively, while in T100 silage,

ADF and NDF were the lowest with 29.85% and 43.66%, respectively. While crude oil rate was 2.74% in G100 silage, it decreased to 1.18% in T100 silage. As guar content increased, crude ash rate also increased. The highest crude ash rate was observed in G100 (10.73%) silage and the lowest in T100 (6.56%) silage. Guar has higher crude protein rate than teff and the increase in guar content increased the crude protein rate in the silage. The crude protein rate was 13.74% in G100 silage and decreased to 7.02% in T100 silage. The lowest fleig score was observed in G100 (43.10) silage, while the highest fleig score was observed in T100 (83.81) silage. Increasing teff rate increased the fleig score and improved silage quality.

Table 1. Biochemical properties of teff and guar mixture silages

Silages	ADF	NDF	Crude oil	Crude ash	Crude protein	Dry matter	Fleig score
G100	45.35 ^a	62.18 ^a	2.74 ^a	10.73 ^a	13.74 ^a	27.18 ^a	43.10 ^d
G75+T25	38.31 ^b	55.59 ^b	1.87 ^b	10.09 ^b	10.34 ^b	27.05 ^a	75.89 ^c
G50+T50	37.27 ^b	46.05 ^c	1.72 ^c	9.51 ^c	9.66 ^c	25.24 ^b	80.68 ^b
G25+ T75	35.52 ^c	44.75 ^{cd}	1.40 ^d	9.30 ^c	7.52 ^d	23.60 ^c	83.14 ^a
T100	29.85 ^d	43.66 ^d	1.18 ^e	6.56 ^d	7.02 ^e	22.54 ^d	83.81 ^a
LSD	1.15	1.57	0.06	0.29	0.47	0.76	1.99
Sig. Deg.	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

** $p \leq 0.01$; LSD: least significant difference; Sig. Deg.: significant degree

The pH and silage organic acids of teff and guar mixture silages are given in Table 2. The effect of mixture ratios on pH and silage organic acids was statistically significant at 1% level. The highest pH was observed in G100 (5.41) silage and the lowest pH was determined in T100 (4.16) silage. Lactic acid content, which has a very important place in the fermentation of silages, was the lowest in G100 with 1.63% and the highest in T100 with 7.53%. The highest rate of acetic acid was

observed in G100 silage with 6.36% and the lowest rate was observed in T100 silage with 1.67%. The highest butyric acid content was 2.42% in G100 silage and 0.00% in T75 and T100 silages. The highest propionic acid content was observed in G100 silage (0.86%) and the lowest levels were observed in T100 silage (0.36%). The highest ethanol content was 9.03% in G100 silage and the lowest was 1.87% in T100 silage.

Table 2. pH and organic acid values of teff and guar mixture silages

Silages	pH	Lactic acid (%)	Acetic acid (%)	Butyric acid (%)	Propionic acid (%)	ETOH ₂ (%)
G100	5.41 ^a	1.63 ^e	6.36 ^a	2.42 ^a	0.86 ^a	9.03 ^a
G75+Teff25	4.58 ^b	2.56 ^d	4.07 ^b	1.75 ^b	0.72 ^b	6.06 ^b
G50+T50	4.37 ^c	5.50 ^c	3.20 ^c	0.54 ^c	0.69 ^c	2.56 ^c
G25+ T75	4.23 ^d	6.05 ^b	1.81 ^d	0.00 ^d	0.58 ^d	1.90 ^d
T100	4.16 ^e	7.53 ^a	1.67 ^e	0.00 ^d	0.36 ^e	1.87 ^d
LSD	0.03	0.13	0.12	0.04	0.02	0.17
Sig. Deg.	**	**	**	**	**	**

** $p \leq 0.01$; LSD: least significant difference; Sig. Deg.: significant degree

Gas and methane production, metabolic energy (ME) and organic matter digestibility (OMD) values of teff and guar mixture silages are given in Table 3. The effect of mixture ratios on gas-methane production, ME and OMD values was statistically very significant ($p \leq 0.01$). It was determined that the gas production of silage increased (37.25 ml-50.52 ml) as the teff ratio increased. Similarly, methane production increased as the teff ratio

increased. The amount of methane, which was 7.41 ml in pure guar silage, increased to 9.14 ml in teff silage. The lowest metabolic energy was determined in G100 (8.05 MJ kg⁻¹ DM) silage and the highest metabolic energy was determined in T100 (10.04 MJ kg⁻¹ DM) silage. OMD increased as teff content increased. OMSD increased from 58.80% in guar silage to 71.45% in teff silage.

Table 3. Gas and methane production, metabolic energy and organic matter digestibility of teff and guar mixture silages

Silages	Gas (ml)	Methane (ml)	ME (MJ kg/KM)	OMD (%)
G100	37.25 ^d	7.41 ^c	8.05 ^d	58.80 ^d
G75+Teff25	42.85 ^c	8.47 ^b	9.01 ^c	65.38 ^c
G50+T50	46.78 ^b	8.50 ^b	8.99 ^c	64.28 ^c
G25+ T75	47.44 ^b	8.74 ^b	9.60 ^b	68.55 ^b
T100	50.52 ^a	9.14 ^a	10.04 ^a	71.45 ^a
LSD	1.26	0.33	0.18	1.16
Sig. Deg.	**	**	**	**

** $p \leq 0.01$; LSD: least significant difference; Sig. Deg.: significant degree

The study was carried out to improve the nutritional and fermentation properties of teff and guar plants by making mixed silage at different ratios. The results obtained for teff and guar were in accordance with previous studies (Kaplan et al., 2016; Oflaz et al., 2019; Kaplan and Akçura, 2021; Ciftci et al., 2023). When plants with different chemical composition and dry matter are mixed, the components of silage may increase or decrease depending on the mixing ratio (Kizilsimsek et al., 2017). It is reported that differences in dry matter, protein and fiber ratios in plants are due to factors such as genetic structure, differences in spike, leaf and stem ratios, maturation period, environmental characteristics and differences in agricultural practices (Ball et al., 2001). In the study, while the dry matter rate of teff plant was quite low for silage production, it approached the ideal dry matter rate (25-35%) for silage with the increase in the amount of guar (Muck et al., 2003). Low levels of ADF and NDF in feeds are desirable. Increased ADF and NDF content indicates a higher concentration of difficult-to-digest fiber, which reduces digestion and potentially lowers energy availability for ruminants (Kaplan et

al., 2016). In addition, Li et al. (2010) observed that forage plants with lower ADF and NDF values tend to undergo more efficient fermentation and produce higher quality silage. In the study, increasing teff rate caused a decrease in NDF and ADF ratios. Differences in NDF and ADF values vary depending on the type of forage, harvest time of forage and various combinations of forage used (Aderinola et al. 2014). It is important to increase the amount of protein in diets to obtain high yield and quality from ruminant animals (Van Soest, 1994). The increase in guar content in the mixtures caused an increase in crude protein, crude oil and crude ash contents. Increasing the legume ratio in mixture silages made with different plants increased the crude protein, crude fat and crude ash contents of the silage (Muhammad et al., 2008; Parra et al., 2019; Ciftci et al., 2023). Franco et al. (2022) found that changing the proportions of forages in silage can significantly affect protein content, especially when forages have complementary nutrient profiles. In mixture silages made with legume and wheatgrass, increasing the proportion of wheatgrass in the mixture decreases the pH level (Lima et al.

2010). Increased lactic acid decreases the pH of the environment and prevents the development of harmful microorganisms (Acikgoz et al., 2002). It has been reported that carbohydrates decreased with increasing legume ratio and the amount of buffering substances (etc. minerals, protein) increased (Parra et al., 2019). Since the ensiled material is protected by lactic acid, lactic acid bacteria are the most important microflora in the silo (Arslan and Cakmakci, 2011). An increase in lactic acid level means good fermentation and stable silage production. Acetic and propionic acid can increase the aerobic stability of silage, but at high levels they can be an indicator of undesirable fermentation (Ciftci et al., 2023). Butyric acid is an indicator of undesirable Clostridial fermentation and high levels reduce the quality of silage. Ethanol production can indicate the activity of yeast and other undesirable microorganisms and cause energy loss. Therefore, butyric acid and ethanol amounts are expected to be at very low levels in silage. Yücel et al. (2017) reported that acetic acid and $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$ concentrations increased with increasing soybean ratio in their study with corn and soybeans. High concentrations of $\text{NH}_3\text{-N}$, acetic acid, 2,3-butanediol and ethanol indicate that soybeans support the formation of enterobacteria (McDonald et al., 1991). As a result, enterobacteria may be responsible for this increase in ethanol concentration (Parra et al., 2019). The degree of gas production depends on the amount of fermentable carbohydrate and the gas produced as a result of fermentation is a good indicator of the amount of carbohydrate in the microorganism (Blümmel and Orskov, 1993). It has been reported that the amount of gas produced during fermentation is also affected by the presence of secondary metabolites such as tannins and saponins (Kondo et al., 2014). In our study, gas and methane production decreased with the increase in the amount of guar, which has lower carbohydrate levels and higher tannin levels due to being a legume. ME and OMSD contents were calculated using crude oil, ash, protein and gas production values (Menke and Steingass, 1988). In

silages, increase in teff content increased energy and digestibility, while increase in guar content decreased gas and methane production.

4. Conclusion

According to the results of the study, silages made with teff and guar mixture improved the nutritional properties of silage, fermentation properties, gas-methane production, ME and OMD contents. The increase in guar content in the mixture increased dry matter, crude protein, crude oil and crude ash rates and contributed to the reduction of gas and methane production. The increase in teff rate caused a decrease in ADF and NDF content, pH, acetic, butyric and propionic acids and ethanol content, and increased lactic acid content, ME and OMD in fleig score. At the end of the study, G50 + T50 and G25 + T75 mixture ratios are recommended in terms of both nutritional and fermentation properties of the mixture silage.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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